

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF FINANCIAL ORGANIZATIONS USING BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation. In this article, we analyzed the use of Blockchain Technology in the financial management process. The conditions, procedure and specifics of the aspects of technology for implementation in all areas of enterprise management were studied.

Keywords: blockchain, cybersecurity, transaction, cryptocurrency, platform.

Blockchain technology is entering the global arena step by step. A system built on the basis of mathematical algorithms that may be an inevitable technological revolution. Blockchain technology is capable of changing not only the financial services industry, but also many other industries and spheres of society.

For the first time, the term began to be used as the name of a replicated distributed database implemented in the Bitcoin system, that's why the blockchain is often compared with the register of transactions in various cryptocurrencies. However, the technology of block chains can be extended to any interconnected information blocks[1]. The Bitcoin system became the first application of blockchain technology in October 2008[8].

Blockchain is now used in areas such as user identification. financial transactions, cybersecurity technologies[5].

First of all, Blockchain technologies are relevant for banking institutions and government organizations.

In the Russian banking sector, companies such as VTB[7] and Sberbank[10].

VISA [14][15], Mastercard[12][11], Unionpay[3] and SWIFT[4][2] payment systems announced developments and plans to use blockchain technology.

The London Division is developing an investment system based on blockchain technology that accelerates, simplifies and reduces the cost of the investment process by eliminating or reducing the role of intermediaries, lawyers (attorneys), auditors and clearing agents Deutsche Bank Innovation Lab[9].

Based on Ethereum, S7 Airlines and Alfa-Bank launched a blockchain platform for automating trading operations with agents in July 2017[13].

Uzbekistan has enormous human and intellectual resources for the transition to a new age of technology, which will attract a huge amount of foreign investment in the republic. The use of blockchain technology in the management and financial organizations of Uzbekistan will make it possible to switch to a personalized system, since all episodes of interaction between individuals and legal entities with financial organizations and institutions will be stored in the database.

According to the Concept of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2025, the task is to create a complex of information systems and databases integrated on the basis of unified national standards, writes Review.uz .

In the field of financial transaction management, the issue of information management is very relevant. Banking institutions and government organizations work daily with data that require correct handling, confidentiality, and accurate transmission of information. There are special rules for accessing the data of subjects, algorithms and standards for working with them. Currently, the task is to create a system for storing information about the subjects of the country and providing convenient access to it by banking institutions and government organizations. Blockchain technology opens up very interesting and promising opportunities for data storage, transmission and management.

On November 12, 2018, the first pilot implementation of blockchain technology in Uzbekistan took place within the framework of cooperation between the Uzbek Digital Economy Development Support Fund "Digital Trust" and the Russian company Blockchain Industrial Alliance. Blockchain technology is used in the automated registry system "State Center for Expertise and Standardization of Medicines, Medical Devices and Medical Equipment". In this case, the use of blockchain technology allows you to trace the chronology of the movement of units of products from the supplier to the patient and the facts of the targeted and targeted use of medicines.

Advanced countries in Europe, the USA, Canada and Japan with a developed digital economy have transferred their healthcare using blockchain technology to an online mode that allows conducting research on poorly studied diseases, conducting budget and payment monitoring, ensuring the security of patient data, etc. This platform provides patient health data for medical institutions to improve treatment methods. Users get access to them through the application. The program has the ability to make individual recommendations for each patient.[16]

Fast, accurate and complete all financial transactions, the availability of the possibility of implementation in the corpus is also considered one of the

main achievements of blockchain technology, which also makes it possible to carry out calculations of different levels. Thanks to the use of smart contracts, blockchain technology creates a number of opportunities.

In particular, as a result of the implementation of interaction with counterparties in the mode of smart contracts, the enterprise can be used to verify the activities of counterparties, eliminate problematic situations associated with them. For example, in the process of corporate financial management, it will be possible to effectively carry out financial transactions, such as debit and credit debt management. The fact that Blockchain technology can also be used as a new trading platform makes it possible to reduce the cost of trading operations, optimize trading activities, and reduce the time limits that will be spent on the process of signing trade deals.

The introduction of blockchain technology in the process of corporate financial planning can serve as a guarantee of achieving economic efficiency. Transactions directly between two parties without the participation of a third party, ensuring their quick and easy implementation, it will be possible to automatically manage smart contracts and commercial activities. Thus, it directly regulates each process and reduces the negative impact of the time factor.

It should also be pointed out that there is no long-term practical experience in using blockchain. Most of the technological solutions using blockchain are only a few years old, and some of them are under development. There was not enough long-term practice to fully test them in working conditions, which increases security risks and the cost of development and implementation.

Blockchain technology provides an opportunity to conduct a full audit of the process, prepare various analytical reports on the details of each transaction, conduct research on them, determine the level of hidden risks in advance, and develop measures to eliminate them. This position allows everyone to authenticate data, assets and make corporate financial planning decisions. Creation of the possibility to fully implement the monitoring process, it will be possible to exercise financial control at every stage of the trading chain, effectively controlling the work. As a result of the introduction of blockchain technology, the principle of transparency is fully functioning, the database related to each stage of corporate financial planning is transparent for each participant, which allows for individual control.

Nowadays, provision of the database in business processes will allow most to provide solutions to problematic situations.

Even if there are solutions involving a private or authorized blockchain and strong encryption, it is worth recognizing that there are also cybersecurity issues that need to be addressed before the general public provides their personal data.

Blockchain software also requires significant modification or complete replacement of existing systems.

In addition, further improvement of blockchain technology is required today in the following direction:

- theft of end-user personal data;
- create an opportunity to identify fake senders and recipients in a timely manner;
- theft of assets and nodes or termination of the process of taking possession of another person;
- targeting bitcoin creators (miners) ;
- fast detection of the presence of distributed nodes and restriction of the entry of malicious code into the distributed registry;
- restrict incoming and outgoing information;[6]

This is a kind of prevention of theft of transaction details, personal data.

Technologies and trends are becoming increasingly interconnected and integrated, which gives a powerful impetus to innovation in the field of financial technology and the financial industry.

On April 8, 2022, the 6th Meeting of Heads of Ministries and Departments of Science and Technology of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization member states was held in Tashkent. As part of this event, Uzbekistan proposed to hold the first digital fair of innovative technologies of the SCO countries in Tashkent, the news agency "Dunyo" reports.[17]

Offering to hold a fair of innovative technologies, the Uzbek side emphasized that the widespread introduction of digital technologies and advanced IT solutions is crucial for the dissemination of innovations and transfer within the SCO.

Perhaps closer integration of IT technologies and the digital economy will increase the efficiency of working with more complex business scenarios and further simplify the provision of financial services.

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